

CODECO

Cognitive Decentralised
Edge Cloud Orchestration

D15: AI Governance and Resilience Aspects in CODECO Version 1

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Executive Summary

Deliverable D15 of CODECO (*CODECO AI Governance and Resilience Aspects*, M18, June 2024) corresponds to an intermediate deliverable of WP5, T5.1. T5.1 focuses on developing and applying an assessment methodology towards the capability of the AI-based cross-layer CODECO orchestration to handle heterogeneous data sets, reduce manual oversight and to support resilience against attacks across Cloud-Edge application deployments. The final release of this deliverable is set for December 2025.

Having as starting point the technological boundaries developed in WP2, this deliverable focuses on an analysis on key aspects to set up an AI governance and resilience methodology suitable for the AI-based orchestration aspects of CODECO, covering the following aspects:

- Methodology to evaluate requirements regarding the robustness and resilience of CODECO,
- Mechanisms to ensure the framework adequacy and robustness in the case of external changes, or different data quality,
- Mechanisms to ensure CODECO transparency and explainability, as well as replicability.

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List of Acronyms and Definitions

Acronym	Meaning
ACM	Automated Configuration Management
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AI Act	Artificial Intelligence Act
AIA	Artificial Intelligence Act
AJL	Algorithmic Justice League
ALTAI	Assessment List for Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence
AR	Academia and Research
AR	CODECO stakeholder group Academia and Research
CEI	Cloud-Edge-IoT
CLAIRE	Confederation of Laboratories for Artificial Intelligence Research in Europe
CODECO	Cognitive Decentralised Edge-Cloud Orchestration
CPU	Central Processing Unit
DEV	CODECO stakeholder group developers
EUS	End-user, citizen
EUS	CODECO stakeholder group end-user
FMTI	Stanford Foundational Model Transparency Index
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GNN	Spatio-Temporal Graph Neural Network
GOV	Government, policy makers
GOV	CODECO stakeholder group policy makers
HE	Horizon Europe
HLEG	High-level Expert Group
HRESIA	Human Rights, Ethical and Social Impact Assessment
ICT	CODECO stakeholder group Industry and SMEs with focus on Information and Communication Technologies
IRCEP	Innovation Research and Community Engagement Programme
K8s	Kubernetes
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LIME	Local Interpretable Model-agnostic Explanations
Mx	Month x of CODECO
MARL	Multi-agent Reinforcement Learning Model
ML	Machine Learning
MNIST	Modified National Institute of Standards and Technology database
MSx	Project Milestone, where x defines the identifier of the milestone
NetMA	Network Management and Adaptation
OSI	Open Systems Interconnection
OSS	Open-source Software
PAI	Partnership on AI
PDLC	Privacy-preserving Decentralised Learning

QoE	Quality of Experience
QoE	Quality of Experience
SDO	Standardisation Development Organisation
SWM	Seamless Workload Migration
TEF	Testing and Experimentation Facilities
XAI	Explainable AI

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1 Introduction

CODECO relies on AI/ML approaches to support a finer-grained orchestration that takes into consideration OSI cross-layer information to provide an optimized deployment of applications across the far Edge and Cloud (Edge-Cloud).

From a technical perspective, it is relevant to address how CODECO can handle heterogeneous data sets across federated, multi-architecture environments, thus reducing manual intervention, and providing the means to support a robust response to potential attacks across Cloud-Edge both during setup and runtime of applications across federated clusters.

For this, the present deliverable covers the work proposed to be developed in the initial 18 months of T5.1 in the context of WP5, which concerns the creation of a methodological framework for AI resilience and governance in CODECO. The main goals are:

- To ensure an adequate data preparation, handling, and pre-processing.
- To propose a way to evaluate requirements regarding the robustness and resilience of CODECO use-cases.
- To ensure the capability of CODECO to answer external changes or variations of data quality in a robust way.
- To ensure CODECO transparency and explainability, as well as replicability.

1.1 Document Scope

D15 corresponds to an intermediate version of the CODECO AI governance and resilience framework. The final version is due in M36 (December 2025). This intermediate deliverable provides the following aspects:

- Explains how and where CODECO relies on AI, and for which purpose, detailing potential issues related with such use.
- Provides a proposal for a methodological approach to allow to test and validate CODECO in terms of AI governance aspects, and AI resilience.
- Provides a set of checklists to periodically assess CODECO in the different proposed dimensions (governance, resilience, security, experimentation).

1.2 Document Structure

The remainder document is organized as follows:

- **Section 2** provides pointers to relevant related work such as European AI related policies, and European projects relevant to the aspects described in this deliverable.
- **Section 3** describes the methodological approach followed to create the CODECO AI governance and resilience framework, providing a timeline with concrete steps to take.
- **Section 4** provides the AI governance principles and how they are handled in CODECO.
- **Section 5** covers AI resilience aspects, and approaches considered by CODECO.
- **Section 6** explains the tools and processes that are being used in CODECO to assess AI resilience and governance impact.
- **Section 7** provides an overview on how CODECO expects to handle adaptations due to external changes (e.g., new legislation, feedback from CODECO stakeholders) or internal changes (e.g., changes or updates in use-cases or CODECO toolkits).

- **Section 8** concludes the document, providing a list of recommendations and next steps concerning the second part of the work.
- **Annex I** provides a set of checklists to be used by the CODECO consortium, and interested partners, to best assess the robustness of AI-based solutions. These will be the basis for the subsequent work of T5.1 in the second period of CODECO (M19-M36).
- **Annex II** provides the template used in CODECO for the AI impact assessment process.

1.3 Document Dependencies

This deliverable is a standalone document. However, to best understand the proposed methodology and the use of AI/ML in CODECO the reading of the following deliverables is advised:

- D2, data management [1]
- D8, use-cases [2]
- D9/D10, CODECO architecture [2]
- D11/D12, CODECO early release (single cluster operation) [4].

2 Relevant Related Work

The CODECO AI governance methodological approach aims at defining the goals, processes, stakeholders, risks, and potential impact of the proposed AI governance and resilience framework. The core focus of this methodology is to allow to assess the AI governance and resilience of CODECO, its framework, components, and use-cases.

In alignment with European policies such as the AI Act¹, and with guidelines from initiatives such as HumaneAI², this section provides a global perspective to the building blocks which are further described in sections 3-9.

2.1 Related Literature

The development of AI technologies has necessitated the establishment of frameworks and guidelines to ensure ethical and responsible usage. Various international initiatives and organizations have contributed to this endeavour by addressing diverse aspects of AI governance and ethical implications.

The *Montréal Declaration on Responsible AI*³ aims to prioritize the well-being of individuals in AI development. It provides ethical guidelines through an inclusive, democratic process involving diverse stakeholders. Designed for developers, organizations, and companies, it supports projects and organizes events like the Summer School on Responsible AI. The Declaration also offers multilingual resources to aid in responsible AI implementation.

The UK Parliament's Science, Innovation, and Technology Committee's interim report⁴, published in August 2023, addresses the rapid advancement of AI technology and the need for effective governance frameworks. The report outlines twelve key challenges, including bias, privacy, misrepresentation, access to data, and existential risk. It emphasizes international cooperation and the importance of a "*pro-innovation approach*" with principles such as safety, transparency, fairness, accountability, and contestability. The report suggests timely legislation is crucial to maintain the UK's leadership in AI governance.

1 <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/regulatory-framework-ai>

2 <https://www.humane-ai.eu/>

3 <https://montrealdeclaration-responsibleai.com/>

4 <https://committees.parliament.uk/publications/41130/documents/205611/default/>

In "*AI and Big Data: A Blueprint for a Human Rights, Social and Ethical Impact Assessment*", Alessandro Mantelero proposes the Human Rights, Ethical and Social Impact Assessment (HRESIA) model. This comprehensive impact assessment focuses on human rights and social implications of data processing, going beyond traditional data protection assessments. The HRESIA model includes a self-assessment questionnaire and an expert committee to evaluate the broader consequences of data practices on fundamental rights and social values [4].

The *Confederation of Laboratories for Artificial Intelligence Research in Europe (CLAIRE)*⁵ is an international non-profit organization founded in 2018. It aims to enhance European excellence in AI research with a human-centred focus. CLAIRE promotes collaboration among its members and advocates for significant investment in AI infrastructure, akin to a "CERN for AI," to establish European leadership in trustworthy AI by 2030.

The *VERSES AI⁶ Governance* addresses global challenges in regulating advanced AI systems, emphasizing socio-technical standards for interoperability, explainability, and autonomy. Combining legal expertise and guidance from the Spatial Web Foundation, the initiative introduces a new AI rating system and tackles key questions about government regulation, fairness, human oversight, and embedding laws in AI systems.

The University of Technology Sydney developed the *AI-resilience diagnostic tool⁷* to help educators assess the vulnerability of their assignments to cheating using generative AI. The tool provides guidelines for adapting assessment tasks to improve integrity and learning outcomes, emphasizing critical thinking, real-world scenarios, diverse formats, and student reflections.

The Fraunhofer *IAIS AI Assessment Catalog⁸* offers a structured approach to evaluating the trustworthiness of AI applications. It includes criteria, methods, and tools to ensure the reliability and responsible use of AI technologies, supporting projects like Certified AI and AI Safeguarding.

The *Partnership on AI (PAI)⁹* is a nonprofit organization that brings together industry, academia, and civil society to ensure AI technologies benefit people and society. PAI focuses on fairness, transparency, accountability, safety, labour, and the economy. It develops best practices, conducts research, and creates guidelines for responsible AI development.

The *Algorithmic Justice League (AJL)¹⁰* is dedicated to mitigating the harms and biases in AI systems. Combining art and research, AJL exposes social implications of AI and advocates for equitable and accountable AI technology through awareness campaigns, empirical research, and engagement with impacted communities, policymakers, and industry practitioners.

The *European Parliament's report on AI governance* provides a comprehensive analysis of the current landscape and future challenges of AI in Europe. It discusses potential economic,

⁵ <https://claire-ai.org/>

⁶ <https://www.verses.ai/>

⁷ <https://lx.uts.edu.au/collections/artificial-intelligence-in-learning-and-teaching/resources/ai-resilience-diagnostic-for-assessment-tasks/>

⁸ <https://www.iais.fraunhofer.de/en/research/artificial-intelligence/ai-assessment-catalog.html>

⁹ <https://partnershiponai.org/>

¹⁰ <https://www.ajl.org/>

social, and ethical impacts, and explores regulatory frameworks to address these issues. The report emphasizes fostering AI innovation while ensuring compliance with European values and legal frameworks, focusing on ethical considerations, transparency, accountability, and human-centric AI development.

UNESCO's initiative on the *Ethics of Artificial Intelligence*¹¹ addresses global ethical implications of AI technologies. It promotes inclusive and participatory dialogue among stakeholders to develop ethical guidelines and frameworks, emphasizing transparency, accountability, and respect for diversity in AI research, development, and deployment. UNESCO aims to foster AI innovation that benefits humanity while mitigating potential risks such as discrimination, bias, and privacy violations.

2.2 Related AI Governance and Resilience Projects

There are several initiatives focusing on the support of AI governance and resilience. These initiatives are designed to bridge the gap between theoretical frameworks and practical, real-world applications, allowing for carefully evaluating and refining governance models before full-scale implementation.

Within the context of CODECO, considering the learnings from related programs, initiatives, and frameworks enables us to tailor our AI Governance and Resilience methodology to diverse environments and use-cases, ensuring its relevance, effectiveness, and adaptability across different sectors and scenarios.

Apart from the definitions of the various aspects of the trustworthiness of AI systems specified in the literature listed in Section 2.1, active developments and frameworks for the creation and operation of trustworthy AI systems produced in other initiatives have influenced the development of a methodological framework for AI resilience and governance in CODECO.

The consortium will consider the H2020 STAR *AI Trustworthiness Framework*¹² as an example to analyse AI governance and resilience in use cases. The STAR framework offers an auditing system to support developers and deployers of AI solutions in production lines. It assists in assessing the trustworthiness of their AI systems through both quantitative and qualitative methods, considering technical, organisational, and social/ethical criteria.

After creating an account¹³, the CODECO component leaders, use-case leaders and AI developers can access and use the framework through the STAR market platform¹⁴. The online tool will lead them to fill out a self-assessment form with a set of questions addressing different aspects of AI systems. More specifically, the form offers a set of questions that evaluate AI models' transparency, explainability, fairness, robustness, ethical compliance, documentation, and human oversight, as well as data integrity, privacy, and security. Each question has a set of answers, as depicted in Figure 1, which component leaders can select depending on their AI system's development and deployment. The framework implements a scoring guide that assigns points to measures within questions, calculating an overall trustworthiness score. Besides the scoring purpose, the answers offer recommendations and suggestions that follow several key standards and guides, including the AI Act for compliance with European Union regulations and guidelines for dimensions like safety, robustness, and fairness, while they align with industry-specific standards and ethical AI development principles. This can be an iterative exercise that CODECO component leaders will follow

¹¹ <https://www.unesco.org/ethics-ai/en/>

¹² <https://star-ai.eu/star-auditing-framework-trustworthy-ai>

¹³ <https://www.market.star-ai.eu/register/>

¹⁴ <https://www.market.star-ai.eu/ai-trustworthiness-framework/>

throughout the development, integration, and deployment of their tools, aiming to continuously improve the AI trustworthiness, governance, and resilience of the CODECO platform.

1. How does your AI system ensure the transparency of AI models and algorithms?
Select all the options that apply.
- The system employs XAI techniques (e.g., LIME, SHAP) to interpret decision-making processes and make them more understandable to humans.
 - The system uses feature importance analysis to identify which factors or features the AI model relies on the most when making decisions.
 - The system is accompanied by comprehensive documentation of the AI system's design, architecture, algorithms, and data sources.
 - The system is accompanied by visual representations of the AI model's internal processes in order to explain complex models to non-technical stakeholders.
 - The system possesses User-Friendly Interfaces that provide insights in to the AI system's behaviour and allow users to interact with the system while understanding its decision- making process.
 - The system comes with auditing tools and dashboards that allow for real-time monitoring of the AI system's performance, including model accuracy and fairness metrics.
 - The system provides information about the sources and quality of training data, including any potential biases in the data.
 - The system complies with applicable and emerging regulations, such as the GDPR, the AI Act and industry-specific standards.
 - The system is subject to regular external by third-party auditors or experts that assess the AI system's transparency and compliance with best practices.
 - Stakeholders engaging with the system are properly trained on transparency principles and practices.

Figure 1: Example on the H2020 STAR AI governance methodology questions.

Another framework that CODECO will consider is the *Assessment List for Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence (ALTAI)*¹⁵, a practical tool that helps organisations to self-assess the trustworthiness of their AI systems under development. Users can access and use the ALTAI portal to transform AI principles into an easily navigable and dynamic checklist.

ALTAI focuses on seven sections for Trustworthy AI: Human Agency and Oversight, Technical Robustness and Safety, Privacy and Data Governance, Transparency, Diversity, Non-Discrimination, and Fairness, Societal and Environmental Well-being, and Accountability. Each section includes a set of subsections, which offers detailed information about their purpose and goals in the AI Trustworthiness framework. In each subsection, users are called to evaluate their systems through a series of questions, as shown in Figure 2. Depending on the provided answers, more questions might be added to each subsection to help users gain insight into whether meaningful and appropriate solutions or processes to accomplish adherence to the requirements are already in place (through internal guidelines, governance processes, etc.) or need to be put in place.

¹⁵ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/assessment-list-trustworthy-artificial-intelligence-altai-self-assessment>

Human Autonomy

This subsection deals with the effect AI systems can have on human behaviour in the broadest sense. It deals with the effect of AI systems that are aimed at guiding, influencing or supporting humans in decision making processes, for example, algorithmic decision support systems, risk analysis/prediction systems (recommender systems, predictive policing, financial risk analysis, etc.). It also deals with the effect on human perception and expectation when confronted with AI systems that 'act' like humans. Finally, it deals with the effect of AI systems on human affection, trust and (in)dependence.

Is the AI system designed to interact, guide or take decisions by human end-users that affect humans ('subjects') or society? *

- Yes
- To some extent
- No
- Don't know

Could the AI system generate confusion for some or all end-users or subjects on whether a decision, content, advice or outcome is the result of an algorithmic decision? *

- Yes
- No

Did you put in place procedures to avoid that end-users over-rely on the AI system? *

- Yes
- No

Please explain:

Did you put in place any procedure to avoid that the system inadvertently affects human autonomy? *

- Yes
- No

Please explain:

Figure 2: ALTAI check on human autonomy.

3 Methodological Approach

Derived from the related literature analysed in section 2 and from discussions within the consortium, the dimensions considered in the CODECO AI governance and resilience methodology are **governance**, **resilience**, **continuous improvement**, and **assessment** as illustrated in Figure 3.

Figure 3: CODECO AI governance and resilience methodological approach, core dimensions.

3.1 Core Dimensions

The key questions regarding **Governance** in CODECO are:

- **Ethical Principles and Values:**
 - Are clear and comprehensive ethical principles and values established for AI development and use in CODECO?
 - How to ensure that these principles address fairness, transparency, accountability?
 - Are there legal and regulatory frameworks in place to govern the development, deployment, and use of AI, and how do they relate with the requirements in CODECO?
 - Do these frameworks adequately address potential risks and ensure responsible AI use in CODECO?
- **AI governance and Lifecycle:**
 - Are there mechanisms in place for valid data acquisition and preparation?
 - Are there mechanisms in place for model development, deployment, adaptation, and validation?
- **Stakeholder Engagement:**
 - How do the CODECO stakeholders relate with the use of AI in CODECO?
 - What are the risks that can be foreseen, and which measures can be used in this context?
- **Transparency and Explainability:**
 - Are the AI approaches in CODECO developed in a transparent and explainable way, allowing for understanding their decisions and potential biases?
 - Does CODECO have specific processes to ensure transparency and address potential concerns, invalid data, or malicious data?

Concerning **Resilience**, this methodology tackles the following aspects:

- **Security and Robustness:**
 - Is AI in CODECO resilient to cyberattacks, manipulation, and adversarial inputs?
 - Are there appropriate measures in place to ensure system security and data integrity, and if so, which measures?
- **Monitoring and Evaluation:**
 - Can CODECO handle errors and unexpected situations gracefully, preventing unintended consequences?
 - Can the AI in CODECO adapt to changing environments and learn from experience? How?
 - Are there continuous monitoring and improvement processes established to maintain the effectiveness and safety of the AI applied in CODECO?
 - Are there clear mechanisms in place for human oversight and control of AI systems, ensuring that they are used within appropriate boundaries and for intended purposes?

The third covered dimension, **Continuous Improvement** focuses on providing measures to adapt the use of AI in CODECO in a responsible and resilient way for emerging changes, e.g., different datasets, or changes in the CODECO operation (e.g., support in a single cluster operation or federated clusters).

The last dimension, **Assessment**, focuses on the use of the proposed principles and tools to continuously evaluate the use of AI in CODECO and its impact on the CODECO assets, and towards target stakeholder groups.

3.2 AI in CODECO

The CODECO OSS framework and its components rely on AI/ML approaches to provide a more flexible and finer-grained management (orchestration) to containerized applications from the far Edge to the Cloud. It should be highlighted that CODECO provides the infrastructure and capabilities to support applications running across the *Cloud-Edge-IoT (CEI)* continuum. AI applications are therefore in this position. AI/ML in the context of CODECO is therefore a technology enabler – CODECO is not directly related to the core functionality of AI.

In CODECO, the purpose of using AI/ML is the following:

- **Supporting real-time data processing:** a first purpose relates to real-time data processing. The data used in this process relates to the CODECO infrastructure (nodes, networks, and data workflow), and may also relate to the applications supported by CODECO, as it occurs in use-cases. The data processing is expected to occur on the Edge. For single cluster operation, it will rely on AI/ML centralized patterns; for federated clusters, it will rely on decentralized AI/ML patterns.
- **Enabling decentralized AI models:** CODECO's framework is expected to handle the deployment of AI models directly on Edge (far Edge, near Edge), which can be beneficial for applications where privacy or low latency is critical.
- **Improving Quality of Experience (QoE):** By enabling real-time data processing and decentralized AI, CODECO can contribute to a better user experience for applications that rely on AI, such as autonomous vehicles or smart factories.

Figure 4 provides an overview of the CODECO components, and where AI/ML is applied to handle specific functions. The functions are summarized as follows:

- AI/ML is used in the CODECO component **Privacy preservation Decentralized Learning (PDLC)** to provide recommendations on where application micro-services should be deployed considering the CEI infrastructure composed of nodes and links, available for specific applications.
- Estimation of a proposed placement based on target profiles provided by the user (e.g., the system should be optimized to reduce energy or to increase resilience) is sent from PDLC to the scheduler that CODECO relies upon within the **Seamless Workload Migration (SWM)** component.
- Detection of abnormal patterns, e.g., networking issues, will (second period of CODECO) be sent to the component that handles the networking aspects, **Network Management and Adaptation (NetMA)**.
- AI/ML is also used in PDLC to analyse infrastructure resource usage, thus feeding the system with predictions about future demands, and requests for a dynamic resource allocation readjustment.
- This information is made available to the user via the **Automated Configuration Management and Security (ACM)** component, and to the CODECO scheduler in SWM.
- SWM makes a weighted decision (hence, AI-driven decision) on re-scheduling allocated resources.
- AI-driven decision-making in CODECO therefore optimizes application workload allocation and reallocation based on factors such as latency, bandwidth, and energy consumption.

Figure 4: AI use in CODECO. The core AI component is PDLC, which provides an estimate on the system stability over time. PDLC provides recommendations for suitable nodes to the CODECO scheduler in SWM. Furthermore, PDLC is expected to provide in the future network state prediction.

3.3 Target Stakeholders and their Relation to the Use of AI in CODECO

CODECO targets the following stakeholder groups based on different initiatives:

- **ICT, Industrial and SME players.** This group comprises vendors and integrators, both large companies and SMEs, involved in the deployment of CEI solutions.
- **GOV, Municipalities, public authorities, policy makers.** Comprises a wide group of public sector stakeholders including municipalities, citizens, smart cities, and public authorities, which benefit from a platform such as CODECO to simplify the deployment of containerized codebase. This group is engaged by Use Cases leaders and by actions related to UC deployments and demos.
- **SDO, Standardization entities and open-source communities.** Relates with normative, pre-normative entities and with open-source alliances and consortia, relevant to the uptake of the CODECO ecosystem. This group is engaged via specific standardization actions led in WP6, T6.3.
- **AR, Academia, and Research.** AR is a key group to spread the benefits of CODECO concepts and technologies, and to provide feedback to, transfer and promote the scientific and technical know-how generated within the project. This target group can be effectively reached through the consortium’s research communities and partnerships with other leading research initiatives and institutions in Europe and beyond, via the channels of all partners.
- **EUS, End-Users. General public.** Correspond to specific end-users in the use-case domains (Manufacturing, Smart Cities, Energy, Smart Buildings). In addition to the use-cases, this group will be engaged in CODECO via the IRCEP programme and by all partners.
- **DEV, software developers and early adopters.** Software developers, with whom CODECO shall interact via the activities developed in WP5 (use-cases), WP6 (dissemination, communication) and WP7 (community building, Innovation and Research Community Engagement Programme for third-party engagement). The DEV group is engaged via the IRCEP programme and via partner ECL coordination in the context of T7.1.

Table 1 provides an overview of the AI aspects in CODECO, and how they relate with the CODECO target stakeholder groups in terms of governance, resilience, and assessment. Regarding continuous improvement, this is an orthogonal core dimension which applies the measures proposed for the other dimensions.

Table 1: CODECO stakeholder groups and AI governance, resilience, and assessment measures.

Group	Governance	Resilience	Assessment
ICT	Guidelines for risk assessment. Ensure explainability.	Focus on security and data quality. Provide open best practices.	Via IRCEP. Via dedicated studies and events – surveys, polls.
GOV	Clearly explain the relevant policies in Europe and how they apply in CODECO.	Provide measures to standardise testing and evaluation. Promote international cooperation and skills training.	Via IRCEP. Via dedicated studies and events – surveys, polls.
SDO	Ensure alignment with existing best practices, e.g., AIOTI, ISO, ITU-T, IEC. Provide recommendations based on CODECO learnings.		Via standardisation events (sessions). Via related SDO initiatives such as

Group	Governance	Resilience	Assessment
			INSTAR ¹⁶ , EUCEI ¹⁷ .
AR	Provide best practices, data sets, demos	Ensure openness and data transparency. Ensure responsible authorship. Explain and ensure data privacy measures.	Via IRCEP. Studies and events – surveys, polls. Via direct cooperation.
EUS	Ensure FAIR data principles and explain them.	Explain potential attacks and measures used in CODECO to circumvent them.	Via IRCEP. Via dedicated studies and events – surveys, polls Via the Website and social network channels
DEV	Inform on key principles before use of CODECO OSS toolkits. Best practices for data handling.	Ensure security measures. Provide ways to monitor and evaluate.	Via OSS community engagement.

4 Governance Aspects

4.1 Ethical Principles and Values

The focus of this section is to provide orientations on ethical principles and values that need to be supported to ensure that the use of AI in CODECO follows responsible, transparent, and FAIR EC guidelines. Accountability is one of the most crucial principles to consider for the governance of AI. It is defined in key documents such as *the High-Level Expert Group (HLEG)*¹⁸ report, the *General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)*¹⁹, and the *Artificial Intelligence Act (AIA)*²⁰. Accountability in AI involves establishing transparent and well-defined responsibilities and obligations related to the design, development, deployment, and use of AI systems. This can be achieved via ethical guidelines and standards for AI development and deployment. This includes data governance, transparency, and explainability.

Within CODECO, teams involved in AI development and deployment are invited to use the template provided in **Annex I, Table 3** during their work to ensure that ethical principles are considered and registered.

In addition, a key principle for AI development concerns the processes implemented regarding data management. The procedures and measures in use in CODECO are described within D2 - Data Management and Ethics Handling v1.0 [1], which focuses on detailing the management of all the data generated by the project following the FAIR principles.

4.2 AI Governance and Lifecycle Management

AI governance refers to all aspects of how the processes for controlling its use are implemented, reviewed, and kept updated, as well as the nature of the processes themselves. AI governance must provide the means to track and analyse which data is used in producing an AI model, what is the expected behaviour of the AI model, how its performance is being monitored as the model changes or new versions are produced, where the AI model is being used, just to name a few. There is no limit to how many aspects of an AI model may be considered to govern and manage its lifecycle (see for example the 100 aspects listed in the

¹⁶ <https://instarstandards.org/>

¹⁷ <https://eucloudedgeiot.eu/>

¹⁸ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/expert-group-ai>

¹⁹ <https://gdpr-info.eu/>

²⁰ <https://artificialintelligenceact.eu/>

*Stanford Foundational Model Transparency Index (FMTI)*²¹). It all depends on the processes being put in place to manage them, which must also comply with relevant regulations, such as the AIA.

4.2.1 AI Model Lifecycle

The following tasks compose any AI model lifecycle, which require well-defined processes for proper AI governance to be possible:

- **Data acquisition and management:** processes controlling the obtention of data used to produce the AI models.
- **Data engineering:** processes referring to how the data is manipulated before being used in AI models.
- **Training:** processes that define how the AI models are produced.
- **Tuning/Alignment:** Processes regarding corrective measures introduced in the production of the AI model to ensure compliance with policies, regulations, etc.
- **Evaluation/Deployment.**

4.2.2 Data Acquisition and Management

Data acquisition is an essential part of the AI model lifecycle management, as it defines the tasks the AI model is trained to perform. The CODECO project details their data management handling in deliverable D2.

This section refers to the data considered “*Experimental*” or “*Research*” in that document. The following are requirements that data should follow (rf. to CODECO D2 as well):

- **Must be catalogued in a repository.** This means that it is always possible to find which data was used to produce a specific version of an AI model.
- **Must have an identifiable and verifiable origin.** This means that the lineage of the data can be always traced to an identifiable source, being a publicly accessible dataset or one produced internally.
- **Must have its nature and contents documented.** A description of the data must be provided, for example in the form of data type (integers, floats, strings, etc), sensitivity of the data (personal information, personal identifiable information, etc), file formats used to store the data, etc. If the data is in tabular form, a description of the contents of each column must also be included.
- **Must be labelled according to its contents.** The information provided above can be used to generate labels for the data that allow us to quickly find and keep track of the type of data being used.
- **The legal scope under which the data may be used must be defined.** If the data was obtained externally, the license under which the data was obtained must be declared so that the correct usage can be determined. Depending on the sensitivity of the data, different legal frameworks may apply and restrictions on what can be done with the data must be considered. These restrictions must be clearly specified with the data.

4.2.3 Data Engineering

An AI model, being a mathematical function, typically requires a numerical input. This means that the data used to generate the AI model must be transformed through several pre-processing steps. These steps are as varied as the type of data the task an AI model is

²¹ <https://crfm.stanford.edu/fmti/May-2024/index.html>

designed to fulfil requires. For example, for an AI model using text as input, steps such as document deduplication, abusive language elimination and token generation are typical, independent of how they are implemented.

The mechanisms by which data is pre-processed for use in the generation of an AI model must be documented, including a description of what the processes accomplish, repositories where the code performing those tasks is stored, etc. This section refers to the data considered “**Research**” or “**Derived**” in the CODECO deliverable D2.

4.2.4 Training

Training is the most critical part of the AI model lifecycle, as it defines what the AI model task will be. Training is the process by which the AI model is exposed to input data and the corresponding results which are expected for the AI model to produce, such that through an optimization algorithm applied to the parameters of the mathematical function underlying the AI model a certain threshold of accuracy in the results is reached.

Many aspects of the training process may be documented for compliance with regulatory and policy frameworks:

- The method by which the AI model is being trained: algorithms, number of iterations, number of samples used for training and testing of the results, etc.
- The data used in the training process and the characteristics thereof (see Section 4.2.2).
- The amount of energy used during the training, which is usually a very compute-intensive process.

4.2.5 Tuning/Alignment

Generic AI models may be further refined by “tuning” them for specific tasks. The tuning of the model (similarly to training, see Section 4.2.4) and its specific purpose must be declared with the AI model.

Alignment is the process by which an AI model is fine-tuned so that the output respects certain constraints. This, again, completely depends on the nature of the task the AI model is trained to perform. For example, an AI model generating text may not produce sentences containing certain words or refer to certain topics; an AI model in charge of controlling the resources allocated to a task may not allow for more than a pre-established maximum amount to be dedicated to a single individual task, etc. These safeguards must be declared so that the users of the AI model understand the behaviour to be expected when deployed.

4.2.6 Evaluation/Deployment

Before and during deployment for an actual production task, AI models must be evaluated on how they are performing. This allows us to keep track of potential deficiencies introduced in the AI model as it is developed through different iterations.

An AI model should be evaluated against benchmarks established for the suitability of the model for the tasks it is intended to perform. The producers of the AI model may develop custom benchmarks themselves when the task is sufficiently specific or unique. Standard, publicly available benchmarks are preferred for more generic, regulated or industry-specific tasks, as they provide a more objective metric of the performance of the model, free of the biases of the developers of the model itself. In any case, the benchmarks the AI model is subjected to, and their results must be documented with each produced version of the model.

Risks associated with the AI model must also be documented. Ideally, these should be provided in the form of benchmarks, such as the probability of the model producing an output outside the range of what is desired. At the very least, the risks that the utilization of an AI model imposes on a system and its users must be described so that they can be considered, and countermeasures can be provided.

4.2.7 Standard Mechanisms

As the AI model generation industry matures, standard mechanisms for at least some of the tasks and processes we have outlined have emerged.

Model cards [6] are documents attached to an AI model providing evaluation of said model (ideally through benchmarks) in the context of the task the AI model is designed to fulfil. HuggingFace²², for instance, provides model cards for many of the huge collection of AI models stored in their repositories, which can serve as examples of how to document the AI models developed and used in CODECO. Model cards provide a simple documentation mechanism allowing AI models characteristics to be tracked for governance and lifecycle management purposes.

Kubeflow²³ has emerged as the standard mechanism to run AI workloads on Kubernetes. Running the processes by which AI models are generated in a standard framework makes it easier to track how the training of the models is configured, the resources consumed during the process, which data is being used as input, etc.

Benchmarks are required to keep track of the performance of the AI models both on the task it is intended to do, and the constraints imposed on it by policy and regulatory frameworks. CODECO needs to design benchmarks showing how the AI models perform, in that for example variation of certain values of the input parameters produce an expected scheduling result for an application.

4.2.8 CODECO Questionnaire for AI Model Governance

Given the steps for the AI model lifecycle outlined above and the standard mechanisms proposed, use-case leaders and component leaders are expected to fill in the questionnaire provided in **Annex I, Table 4**. The information is expected to be made publicly available as a model card via the CODECO Eclipse GitLab repository, to allow for change tracking and versioning.

4.3 Transparency, Explainability and Bias

In recent years, the emergence of complex algorithms based on Deep Learning and Gradient Boosting has led to a surge in the need for explainable systems. This necessity arises to provide accountability and transparency to models that are not intrinsically explainable, enabling end-users to detect and limit potential biases in AI-driven systems. Furthermore, the exponential growth in AI-based systems has highlighted the necessity to shield the outcomes of all kinds of AI from hallucinations. Transparent AI fosters trust, aids in accountability, and allows stakeholders to comprehend AI processes, which is crucial to reduce cognitive bias when end-users assess information generated from automatic decision-making.

²² <https://huggingface.co/docs/hub/model-cards>

²³ <https://www.kubeflow.org>

In this context, two main research topics have emerged to mitigate those risks: i) **Explainable AI (XAI)**, with a special focus on quantifiable metrics to measure the explainability of an AI model, and ii) **bias detection** to assess the datasets used in training AI models. These research topics are explained next.

4.3.1 Quantifiable Explainable AI

XAI systems can successfully augment the information provided to stakeholders aside from the results of the AI models, enabling a layer of transparency and accountability and reducing bias and false positives in the system. The explanations should be formulated to be safe for use in critical sectors and are established to the following fundamental principles:

- **Robustness:** explanations should remain consistent and stable in the face of variations in the input data.
- **Human-centric:** explanations should be technically transparent but also tailored to the needs of the end-users. Different users may have different requirements for explanations.
- **Monitoring:** the proposed explanations should be objectively quantifiable and capable of comparing the quality of an explainer from a qualitative point of view.

In CODECO, and as explained in section 3, the use of AI is mostly derived from within the PDLC component which has as input cross-layer data collected from other CODECO components (MDM, NetMA, ACM, cf. to section 3) and employs it in training multiple AI models to perform different objectives.

Currently, two such models are under development: (1) a *Spatio-Temporal Graph Neural Network (GNN)* to forecast resource consumption of CODECO nodes, and (2) a *Multi-Agent Reinforcement Learning model (MARL)* to recommend node allocations based on different application characteristics. Specific information about the AI technical application can be found in the architectural deliverables of CODECO (D9/D10) and in the deliverables that provide an overview on the CODECO OSS Toolkits (D11/D12).

Given the two types of models at hand, we recommend using a model agnostic XAI technique to provide holistic and homogeneous explanations across the two models. The most common model agnostic XAI techniques are the following [7]:

- **Principal Components Analysis (PCA):** PCA is a traditional dimensionality reduction technique which can also be applied as an explainability method when used to identify the most relevant features that affected the outcome of an AI model. PCA works by linearly transforming data onto a new coordinate system such that the directions (principal components) capturing the largest variation in the data can be easily identified [8].
- **Local Interpretable Model-agnostic Explanations (LIME):** LIME is a model-agnostic XAI method that perturbs the input around its neighbourhood and sees how the model's predictions behave to figure out what parts of the interpretable input are contributing to the prediction. LIME weighs these perturbed data points by their proximity to the original data point and fits an interpretable model to explain the predictions. The output of LIME is a set of explanations representing the contribution of each feature to a prediction for a single sample, which is a form of local interpretability [8][9][10].

4.3.2 Bias Detection

Detecting and mitigating bias in AI models is paramount in ensuring fairness, equity, and accuracy in their outcomes. As AI systems increasingly pervade various facets of our lives, from hiring processes to healthcare diagnostics, they wield significant influence and decision-making power. However, these systems are only as unbiased as the data they are trained on. Biased datasets can perpetuate and even exacerbate societal inequalities, leading to discriminatory outcomes that adversely affect certain demographics. Therefore, the motivation behind bias detection in assessing training datasets is to proactively identify and rectify any biases present, thereby fostering trust in AI technologies and promoting inclusivity and fairness in their applications. By scrutinizing the data used to train AI models, we can uncover implicit biases, rectify dataset imbalances, and strive towards more equitable and reliable AI systems. Bias detection should be formulated for safe usage in critical sectors and is established to the following fundamental principles:

- **Inclusivity and Diversity:** involve diverse stakeholders, including individuals from different demographic groups and domain experts, in the bias detection process to ensure a comprehensive understanding of potential biases and their impacts on various communities.
- **Ethical Considerations:** prioritize ethical considerations throughout the bias detection process, considering the potential societal implications and ethical dilemmas associated with the use of AI technologies. Uphold principles of fairness, justice, and equity in all decisions and actions.
- **Continuous Evaluation and Improvement:** Continuously evaluate and improve bias detection techniques based on feedback from stakeholders, emerging research findings, and real-world experiences. Adapt and refine the process to address evolving challenges and mitigate new forms of bias.

AI plays a central role in the CODECO framework developed in this project, where the PDLC component integrates cross-layer data collected from other CODECO components, which eventually are used in AI model training that targets different AI tasks. Currently, two different categories of data are being integrated: i) raw monitoring data, e.g., memory and Central Processing Unit (CPU) usage, and ii) context awareness data, e.g., resilience and greenness costs.

Data type-agnostic bias detection techniques can be leveraged and incorporated into PDLC, aiming to provide a homogeneous and all-inclusive detection across different data types, which in our case consist of two data types. The most common type-agnostic bias detection techniques are the following:

- **Fair Representation Learning:** This approach involves learning a representation of the data that disentangles the underlying factors of variation while removing sensitive attributes. By learning a fair representation of the data, models can make predictions that are independent of protected attributes, thus reducing bias.
- **Causal Inference:** Causal inference techniques aim to uncover causal relationships between variables in the data, which can help disentangle biases that arise from confounding variables. By identifying causal relationships, researchers, professionals, and developers can better understand and address biases in the data.

4.3.3 CODECO Questionnaire for AI transparency

A questionnaire including the main aspects related to explainable AI and bias detection to be filled in for the use of PDLC and for any use-case where PDLC is involved is provided in **Annex I, Table 4**.

5 Resilience Aspects

5.1 Security and Resilience - Infrastructure

Within the CODECO framework, which serves as a highly adaptive Edge-Cloud management tool aiming to deliver dynamic and efficient cross-layer orchestration, numerous considerations must be outlined to adapt proper guidelines and disciplines for delivering secure AI-based services to optimally orchestrate the entire ecosystem. The CEI ecosystem and its respective intercommunication aspects are generally vulnerable to various security threats throughout the entire process, ranging from initial data collection and preparation to training, inference, and final model deployment. Communication among nodes is also a critical aspect.

Given the integral role AI in CODECO's orchestration processes, the potential security threats not only impact the underlying infrastructure but also the AI systems themselves. These threats can compromise the integrity, performance, and reliability of AI-driven decisions and actions within the framework.

The typical types of cyber-threats aiming at downgrading the system's performance, integrity and resilience are partitioned in three fundamental categories and listed next:

- **Edge device-oriented threats:**
 - **Unauthorized edge devices access** [11]: Unauthorized access in edge nodes indicates the unauthorized entry or manipulation of data, such as user's sensitive data (i.e., geo-location, legal information and more), resources, or functionalities living within the edge computing environments. These incidents can occur through various means, such as exploiting vulnerabilities in software or hardware, circumventing access controls, or intercepting communication channels.
 - **Malware Injection Attacks** [12]: Resource-constrained edge devices face challenges in implementing comprehensive firewalls, making them vulnerable to malware injection attacks. These attacks involve attackers covertly installing malicious software on targeted systems.
 - **Misuse events** [13]: Implies the unauthorized utilization of resources, functionalities, or data within edge computing environments for malicious or unauthorized purposes. In this type of security, the impostor detects and exploits the vulnerabilities in AI algorithms or systems to gain unauthorized access, manipulate data, or disrupt operations.
- **Data oriented threats:**
 - **Tampering events** [14]: Refer to the transmission of "false or corrupted" data that may be shared among the interconnected edge nodes.
 - **Data theft incidents** [15]: Refers to the unauthorized acquisition, copying, or extraction of sensitive or confidential data from edge computing environments for illicit purposes. It refers to the risk of data breaches and illegal data exposure.
- **AI-model oriented threats:**
 - **Illegal exploitation of the AI-model inference** [16]: Refers to the unauthorized or malicious use of AI models or inference capabilities within edge computing

systems for illicit purposes. This may involve manipulating AI models to generate inaccurate or biased results, using inference capabilities to perform unauthorized actions, or exploiting vulnerabilities in AI algorithms to bypass security measures. More than that, in such a type of threat, the impostors can modify the models' algorithms to make them perform poorly or behave unfairly. Also, they can manipulate the model's output to spread false information or engage in fraud (evasion and adversarial attacks).

- **Gradient based attacks** [17]: Such attacks are the most potent as the attacker may use the model gradients to gain insights into the working of the model and can then mathematically optimize the attack. This approach is the most probable one to target hardened models, as it has been shown that if an adversary has access to the model gradients, it is always possible to generate adversarial samples irrespective of the robustness of the model.

By understanding and addressing these threats, the CODECO framework can enhance its security posture, ensuring robust protection for AI-based services and the overall CEI ecosystem.

5.1.1 Ensuring a Highly Secure CEI Infrastructure

The challenge around providing secure and resilient edge computing and AI systems outlines the disciplines that must be followed to design edge computing systems and services that can be considered transparent and ethical. Also, these disciplines must take into consideration the compliance with GDPR. Securing both the AI models in AI applications and the system as an overall, is highly important and a multitude of mitigation strategies have been proposed to implement robust security measures avoiding the potential catastrophic loss when cyber-security threats raised:

- AI model encryption techniques (i.e., Differential Privacy [18]).
- Data encryption techniques (i.e., Data Masking [19], Tokenization [20], White Noise [21]).
- Secure data transfer over networks mechanisms (i.e., Secure Sockets Layer, Secure File Transfer Protocols).
- Anti-code lifting mechanisms (i.e., Binary Protection, Code Encryption [21]).

5.1.2 Adversarial Defence Strategies

In the development and deployment of the CODECO framework, it is imperative to consider robust adversarial defence methodologies to ensure the resilience and security of the entire ecosystem. To further enhance these crucial aspects, adversarial defence strategies must be employed. These strategies ensure that security and resilience remain top priorities, adapting to the types of threats to safeguard the AI lifecycle, insights, models, and data generated, collected, and utilized by the functionalities provided by the CODECO framework. To establish and implement such adversarial strategies, a structured approach is necessary. The steps required to ensure high levels of resilience and security within the CODECO ecosystem are meticulously presented in the form of a checklist. This checklist requires input from both the use cases and the CODECO framework itself to assess the level of risk and devise mitigation strategies. The detailed checklist is provided in **Annex I, Table 5** (section: Security), where each CODECO use case offers insights regarding its proximity to these threats, thereby assessing the likelihood and potential impact of such threats.

5.2 Evaluation and Experimentation

Monitoring and evaluation methodology is a crucial aspect of the AI governance and resilience framework, involving a diverse set of evaluation tools and techniques to characterize the performance of AI systems. Ideally, the evaluation framework should systematically address the entire lifecycle of the AI solution, i.e., from data collection and preprocessing to model training, evaluation and serving. This framework needs to assess key components of AI pipelines, such as accuracy, bias mitigation, trust and compliance, transparency, and reliability. Additionally, an efficient evaluation approach should consider the interdependencies between design objectives and evaluation methods, enabling informed choices during the design cycles.

CODECO focuses on the optimal and efficient support of services within Edge-Cloud ecosystems through the deployment of an intelligent Edge-Cloud management framework. From this point of view, the evaluation framework needs to systematically consider restrictions and performance requirements inherent to the edge, in order to assess the suitability of the implemented ML/AI approaches, such as: i) system responsiveness, resource and energy consumption, ii) applicability in highly distributed and heterogeneous environments, both in terms of computation and networking properties, and, iii) validity in handling and accommodating large amounts of data.

In the context of CODECO, we propose the **CODECO experimentation framework**²⁴ [22], an open-source Kubernetes-based solution tailored for experimenting in the Edge-Cloud continuum. The experimentation framework introduces innovative abstractions for the holistic deployment of Kubernetes (K8s) clusters and declarative cross-layer experiment configuration. Aiming to evaluate AI/ML solutions in a declarative and automated manner, the CODECO experimentation framework introduces automation features that cover the entire experimental process (from the configuration up to the results visualization), which may significantly contribute towards intelligent and automated ML/AI evaluation in the entire AI lifecycle. Also, being based on a microservice architecture, this framework is fully configurable and extensible, i.e., can be independently extended to accommodate additional ML/AI methods, as well as on-demand technologies, and features (such as Grafana K6²⁵ and KubeFlow²⁶).

Currently, the CODECO experimentation framework provides the following advantages for monitoring and evaluation of AI/ML approaches over Edge-Cloud environments: i) holistic experimental definitions for all layers of the protocol stack and main K8s features, including the support of alternative edge infrastructures (e.g., choice of hypervisor and server hardware) and virtualization technologies, to accommodate the diversity of edge cloud demands, ii) appropriately designed abstractions to reduce experimentation complexity, iii) advanced automation and reliability, enabling the execution of experiments with different combinations of cross-layer parameters, that may also serve as reference points to evaluate a diverse set of intelligent algorithms, spanning from ML to optimization techniques. Along these lines, the framework also possesses additional advantages: i) reproducible experimentation with one-liner commands and versioning of components, ii) minimal operational support and risk since the deployments can be easily deleted and then re-configured, and iii) support for crucial

²⁴ <https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project/experimentation-framework-and-demonstrations>

²⁵ <https://k6.io/>

²⁶ <https://www.kubeflow.org/>

performance metrics related to resource utilization, i.e., CPU and memory consumption. Note that, an initial investigation by Koukis et al. has already demonstrated CODECO's Experimentation Framework capabilities to pragmatically assess the performance of *anomaly detection (AD)* algorithms over real Edge-Cloud testbeds with promising results [24].

CODECO monitoring and evaluation methodology targets the following emerging concepts, regarding the applicability of the AI/ML approaches in the Edge-Cloud continuum:

- **Real-world and large-scale AI systems evaluation.** This approach goes beyond traditional evaluation strategies, which often focus on small-scale datasets, by also partially assessing the various components of the AI lifecycle. By prioritizing the evaluation of large-scale systems, we aim to capture the complexities and challenges inherent in deploying AI at scale. This includes examining how AI models perform in real-world scenarios, handling large volumes of data, and addressing issues related to resource constraints, scalability, efficiency, and reliability. By adopting this comprehensive evaluation approach, CODECO seeks to ensure that AI systems are rigorously tested and validated under conditions that closely resemble their operational environments, ultimately enhancing their effectiveness and robustness. This methodological framework also involves the comprehensive evaluation of CODECO's use-cases.
- **Interplay between theoretical algorithmic properties and their impact on the Edge-Cloud resources.** Pragmatically assessing the impact of AI algorithms in Edge-Cloud environments provides the means to enrich the performance evaluation of the different AI techniques. In this case, the performance of the AI procedure is not measured explicitly by the evaluation metric (e.g., F1-score or recall) but also by system indicators, such as response time and memory, CPU, or energy consumption. Also providing feedback on the relation between the model and system metric. Of course, the system metric across the different use-cases may vary, e.g., response time when latency is a strict requirement or energy consumption in an IoT scenario. Moreover, exploiting the CODECO experimentation framework, the effect of the resource constraints on performance efficiency may be evaluated. Note for example, that a computationally complex algorithm may perform poorly under limited resources, while a less accurate but lightweight algorithm may lead to quicker responses.
- **Impact of heterogeneity,** in terms of incorporated technologies and network specifications, in the performance of the AI/ML methods. A crucial aspect on evaluating the suitability of ML/AI mechanisms in CODECO's framework is their alignment with the demands of the Edge-Cloud ecosystem. This underscores the limitations of existing AI evaluation framework which are typically designed for centralized clouds or high-performance datacentres. Since the Edge-Cloud environment is characterized by a high degree of heterogeneity, encompassing a variety of devices, virtualization technologies, and communication protocols. Moreover, the CODECO project exploits the adaptation of federated and distributed learning approaches (especially regarding the PDL component), which also demand the collaboration of different devices, even under challenging connectivity conditions. Thus, CODECO experimentation methodology should support experiments over heterogeneous physical and virtual resources through a common abstraction. For instance, prior related work by Koukis et al. highlights how the choice of the Kubernetes flavour and network plugin impacts the resource utilization and the response time of the chosen ML procedures [23]. Finally, it is of paramount importance for the AI/ML evaluation on the edge to consider an end-to-end view.
- **Resilience aspects.** Enhancing cost efficiency, resource utilization and overall system resilience is of paramount importance for the experimentation framework's efficiency. In this direction, anomaly detection algorithms and root cause analysis may be applied, e.g.,

alerting for potential abnormalities in the resource utilization during the experimentation phase. Apart from the detection of failures or inefficiencies, ML and heuristic optimization techniques may also be utilized for resource reallocation and configuration adjustments, targeting the smooth operation of the CODECO's experimentation framework. Finally, within the domain of security and privacy, and ethical principles, CODECO's monitoring, and evaluation methodology is fully aligned to the guidelines described in section 4.1.

5.3 Resilience Questionnaire

To assess the potential resilience and security, partners should rely on the questionnaire proposed in **Annex I, Table 6**.

6 Continuous Improvement

In the context of the CODECO project, it is imperative to ensure that AI systems are developed and deployed responsibly, adhering to ethical standards and regulatory requirements. Responsible AI aims to create systems that are fair, transparent, accountable, robust, and aligned with human values. It serves as a critical checkpoint where various aspects of data analysis, AI-based decision-making, and policy adherence are evaluated and potentially revised.

During the review phase, data analyses are scrutinized to ensure accuracy, integrity, and compliance with established standards. This involves assessing the methodologies used, the quality of the data inputs, and the validity of the insights derived. Any discrepancies or issues identified during this process can trigger adjustments or refinements to improve the overall effectiveness of the data analysis pipeline. Moreover, the review phase extends to the examination of AI-based decisions. Here, the focus is on verifying whether the decisions made by AI models align with predefined criteria, ethical guidelines, and regulatory requirements. Importantly, the review and adaptation process also encompass review current methods and update policies. This involves evaluating whether the existing policies and guidelines established within the CODECO framework are being effectively implemented and whether they remain relevant considering evolving technological landscapes and regulatory changes. If discrepancies or gaps are identified, adjustments to policies may be necessary to ensure alignment with current best practices and compliance standards.

Lastly, the focus on security and privacy is in line with regulatory frameworks like GDPR, stressing human oversight, technical robustness, and data governance protocols. Prioritizing these essentials for trust in AI systems while protecting individual rights and privacy.

The Table 6 outline the key aspects of responsible AI, each with a specific focus to guide the development process within the CODECO project.

7 CODECO AI Impact Assessment Processes

Based on the detailed principles, CODECO relies on a set of tools to assess the governance robustness, resilience, and the potential impact that the use of AI in CODECO may have on the CODECO stakeholders. AI impact assessment is the process of systematically evaluating the potential consequences, both positive and negative, of AI technologies on the various CODECO target group stakeholders.

7.1 Tools

CODECO considers three types of tools to develop a continuous impact assessment, from M19 until M36:

- **Surveys and questionnaires directed to:**
 - The consortium, in particular component leaders and the use-case leaders. The initial questionnaires are provided in Annex I. The surveys will be conducted every three months.
 - The CODECO target stakeholders, derived from existing open tools, and expected to be provided to CODECO target stakeholders during the CODECO events, in particular events such as demo camps, Hackathons.
- **Scenario analysis**, based on the CODECO use-cases. The scenario analysis will cover all CODECO use-cases and will be developed continuously, based on the timeline provided in Figure 5.
- **Experimental Tools and Benchmarks**, focusing on the technological operation of CODECO, e.g., how the use of malicious data may impact the overall CODECO operation.
- **Benchmark Datasets** such as the Modified National Institute of Standards and Technology Database (MNIST)²⁷, CIFAR-10 and CIFAR-100²⁸, ImageNet²⁹.
- **Experimental open platforms** such as open AI Gym³⁰, TensorFlow Neural Network Playground³¹.

7.2 Best Practices

The tools considered will adopt the following best practice principles:

- Adopt a holistic approach to AI impact Assessment, considering economic, social, environmental, ethical, and legal dimensions.
- Engage with stakeholders through the assessment process to gather diverse perspectives and ensure comprehensive coverage of potential impacts.
- Use a combination of qualitative and quantitative methods to assess the multidimensional impacts of AI technologies accurately.
- Incorporate uncertainties and sensitivity analysis into impact assessments to account for the inherent uncertainties and variability in AI technologies.
- Regularly review and update impact assessments to reflect changes in technology, regulations, and societal needs over time.

²⁷ <https://datasets.activeloop.ai/docs/ml/datasets/mnist/>

²⁸ <https://www.cs.toronto.edu/~kriz/cifar.html>

²⁹ <https://www.image-net.org/>

³⁰ <https://github.com/openai/gym>

³¹ <https://playground.tensorflow.org>

7.3 Assessment Processes, Criteria, and Responsibilities

7.3.1 Processes

The impact assessment process is structured to outline the necessary steps to accomplish the established goals. Utilizing a value chain approach, this process consists of the following stages, as depicted in Figure 5. These steps provide a tailored approach for assessing and improving the AI governance and resilience of CODECO, ensuring it aligns with ethical standards, regulatory requirements, and stakeholders' expectations.

- **Methodology Definition** - This first step, described in this deliverable, involves the definition of the methodology to be used to guide the assessment process. This includes establishing the core principles and procedures for evaluating AI governance and resilience within CODECO. The methodology ensures a structured and consistent approach to assessment, incorporating relevant standards and best practices.
- **Data Collection** – Gather comprehensive data to support the assessment. Collect both qualitative and quantitative data relevant to CODECO's AI framework. In this step, FOR as T5.1 lead, will interact with T5.2 lead (UPRC) and with use-case leaders as well as with WP4 and component leaders to collect the required information based on the templates presented in Annex I.
- **Analysis** – Process and interpret the collected data to gain insights. Use analytical tools and techniques to analyse the data. Identify patterns, trends, and potential issues in CODECO's AI governance and resilience. Focus on area like data quality, model performance, security vulnerabilities, and compliance with ethical standards. For this, FOR as T5.1 leader will provide a first check and go back to the respective partner if additional information is required.
- **Evaluation** – Assess CODECO against predefined criteria. Compare the analysed data against benchmarks and standards relevant to AI governance and resilience. Evaluate how CODECO's AI orchestration meets these criteria. Highlight strengths, weakness, and areas needing improvement. The evaluation will be provided by two partners for each component of the proposed methodological approach, based on the criteria described next, and relying on the template provided in Annex II, Table 8. The template will be made available as an Excel file to partners under WP5, T5.1.
- **Reporting** – document the findings and communicate them to stakeholders. Based on the proposed grading by the assigned reviewers, FOR will prepare a detailed report outlining the assessment process, data analysis, evaluation results, and recommendations. An agile format, based on git, will be the basis for this reporting step.
- **Feedback** – Gather stakeholders feedback on the assessment findings and recommendations. Present the report to stakeholders and solicit their feedback. Consider their input to refine the findings and ensure the assessment address all relevant concerns.
- **Review** – validate the assessment process and its outcomes. Conduct a review of the assessment process and findings. Make necessary revisions based on the review to finalize the assessment.
- **Follow-up** – Implement and monitor recommended actions on the assessment. Develop action plans to address the identified issues and opportunities. Implement changes in CODECO's AI governance and resilience framework. Monitor the impact of these actions over time to ensure they are effective and adjust as needed.

Figure 5: Impact assessment processes and timeline.

Partners involved in WP5, Task 5.1, contribute to the overall assessment process based on the template provided in Annex II, Table 8, where a checklist with associated questions to be used to systematically assess each dimension of CODECO, ensuring a thorough evaluation based on multiple criteria and stakeholder perspectives. This will be done based on an Excel provided to partners via the CODECO MS Teams repository, under WP5, T5.1.

7.3.2 Criteria

The proposed criteria (equal weight), evaluated from 1-5 (1 low value; 5 high value) are as follows:

- **Quality:** The overall standard and effectiveness of the system or process.
- **Value Proposition:** The benefit and improvement that the system or process brings.
- **Usability:** How easy and efficient it is to use the system or process.
- **Relevancy:** How pertinent and applicable the system or process is to current needs.
- **Transparency:** The clarity and openness of the system or process.
- **Compliance:** Adherence to legal and regulatory standards.
- **Security:** The measures taken to protect the system from threats.
- **Adaptability:** The ability of the system to adjust to new conditions.
- **Stakeholder Engagement:** The involvement and responsiveness to stakeholders' needs and feedback.
- **Explainability:** How well the system's decisions can be understood by non-experts.
- **Bias Detection:** The system's ability to identify and mitigate biases effectively.

7.3.3 Responsibilities

The distribution of reviewers assigned to each process is presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Assignment of reviewers to the CODECO AI Impact Assessment.

Methodology component	Collected information	Reviewer 1	Reviewer 2
Ethics and Accountability	Information collected via Table 2	INO	FOR
AI Governance	Information collected via Table 3	IBM	INO
XAI	Information collected via Table 4	I2CAT	ICOM
AI Resilience	Information collected via Table 5	UPRC	ATH
Continuous Improvement	Information collected via Table 6	UPM	FOR
AI Impact Assessment	Evaluation based on Table 7	FOR, based on input by the assigned reviewers.	

8 Summary and Next Steps

This deliverable emphasizes the importance of the developed AI governance and resilience framework for the CODECO project, marking it as an essential step towards ensuring the robustness, transparency, and reliability of AI-based solutions within the project. Here are the main takeaways and next steps:

- **Key Achievements:**
 - Development of a robust methodology for assessing AI governance and resilience.
 - Establishment of guidelines and best practices for data handling, model transparency, and security measures.
 - Provision of tools and processes to monitor and evaluate the AI models in various operational scenarios.
- **Recommendations:**
 - Continuous evaluation and improvement of the AI governance and resilience framework.
 - Regular updates and revisions to adapt to new legislative requirements and stakeholder feedback.
 - Enhanced collaboration with stakeholders to ensure comprehensive coverage and address potential risks effectively.
- **Next Steps:**
 - Implementation of the developed framework across CODECO's use-cases and validation of its effectiveness.
 - Periodic assessments using the provided checklists and questionnaires to ensure ongoing compliance and robustness.
 - Preparation for the final deliverable due in December 2025, incorporating all feedback and further advancements in the framework.

By following these steps, the CODECO project aims to maintain high standards of AI governance and resilience, ensuring the trustworthiness and efficiency of AI, when considered in the CODECO framework.

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Annex I – Templates for AI governance and Resilience Checks

Table 3: Ethics and Accountability template.

Use-case/CODECO Component [insert the name of the AI system you are developing]	
Leading entity	Identify the organisation that is leading the project
Leading responsible person	Identify the main responsible person leading the project. (Name and position in the organisation; contact)
Team members involved	Identify the team members that are involved in the project. (For each member: name)
Checklist	Comments or observations
Which field(s) does the AI system you are developing/deploying address?	identify the AI field of use, e.g., healthcare, justice, finance, etc.
What is the purpose of the AI system you are developing/deploying?	describe the objective and function the AI system is intended to
List the functions included in the AI system you are developing/deploying	e.g., NLP, machine vision, classification, etc
Specify the level of autonomy of the AI system you are developing/deploying	e.g., manual control, decision support, automated decision support, and fully automated
Specify how data necessary for the AI system you are developing/deploying is collected, used, and stored	Identify data sources, datasets used, repositories...
List legal requirements applicable to the AI system you are developing/deploying	e.g., requirements linked to the field of use.
Is there a documentation that explains the AI system's decision-making logic? (Y/N)	If yes, indicate which and where is the documentation available. If no, please ensure that this documentation is made available
Are there defined measures to prevent bias in the AI system you are developing/deploying? (Y/N)	If yes, indicate which and where is the documentation available. If no, please ensure that measures are defined
Are there potential risks concerning the AI system you are developing/deploying? (Y/N)	Please consider not only technical/technological risks, but also risks concerning users, environment, and society.

	If yes, are these risks documented?
Are there independent oversight or auditing mechanisms to review the AI system you are developing/deploying? (Y/N)	If yes, please describe those mechanisms. If no, please ensure that a mechanism is defined and put in place
Is this form a revised version? (Y/N) If yes, please indicate the date of the previous version.	

Table 4: AI governance questionnaire for CODECO.

Use-case/CODECO Component [insert the name of the AI system you are developing]	
Leading entity	Identify the organisation that is leading the project
Leading responsible person	Identify the main responsible person leading the project. (Name and contact; affiliation)
Team members involved	Identify the team members that are involved in the project. (For each member: name)
Checklist	Comments or observations
Data Acquisition and Management	
For each data set you use, did you check D2 and provided the respective data set description	Check D2 guidelines – each dataset needs a specific template
Did you upload the datasets to the CODECO Eclipse repository	If not, explain why
Do the datasets contain personal identifiable information?	
Are they affected by any license that may restrict their use?	
Did you provide the data or is it obtained from third parties?	
Training	
Which datasets from those in the previous list are you using for training?	Provide the data set identifier
Which algorithms are you using to train the model? Which parameter configuration are used for those algorithms? Iterations, initial values, etc.	Provide the algorithms with links; explain the parameter configuration required to train.
How much energy are you using to train the model?	Provide quantified information
Which framework are you using to train the model?	Provide framework and link
Tuning	
Have you documented the intended purpose of the model?	
Have you implemented any safeguards in the model? Which ones?	
Evaluation	
Have you run any benchmarks on the model?	If yes, indicate which and provide a reference
How does it compare with previous benchmarks of previous releases of the model?	
Are there any risks associated with the use of this model?	Describe each risk; provide an impact value for the case of CODECO (1-5).

<p>Is this form a revised version? (Y/N)</p> <p>If yes, please indicate the date of the previous version.</p>

Table 5: Questionnaire, XAI and bias detection in CODECO.

Use-case/CODECO Component [insert the name of the solution/component/product you are developing]	
Leading entity	Identify the organisation that is leading the project
Leading responsible person	Identify the main responsible person leading the project. (Name and position in the organisation)
Team members involved	Identify the team members that are involved in the project. (For each member: name)
Checklist	Comments or observations
XAI¹⁷	
What are possible scenarios to prompt explanations (e.g., understanding inner workings, anticipating user questions, details about data, model mechanics at a high level, and ensuring ethical considerations during model development)?	
What is the explanatory strategy (e.g., internal explanation, external or post-hoc explanation, counterfactual explanation)?	This depends on the explainability method and the model type. (for instance, LIME is a post-hoc explanation method)
What is the trade-off between explainability and other requirements of the AI model such as security and intellectual property?	
What is the trade-off between the explainability and performance of the AI model?	The higher / more detailed the explanations are the more deterioration in the model performance there is
Who are the stakeholder groups in need of an explanation (e.g., customers, regulators, internal officers, risk managers, senior management, model validators)?	
How will the explanation be conveyed to stakeholders (e.g., in person, by a system)?	Usually done automatically by a system
What is the degree of interaction between the human and the machine in conveying to the owner the explanation (e.g., declarative, one-way interaction, two-way interaction)?	
What are the evaluation measures of the XAI system (e.g., user mental model, usefulness and satisfaction, model performance)?	
How to measure stakeholder satisfaction with the explanations provided (e.g., user engagement, Likert scale questionnaires, simulated experiments)?	
Bias Detection¹⁸	

How much do I understand the domain?	
Should I consider the sample size? E.g. time window of infrastructure resources?	
Is the data representative?	
What are these variables? How much should I know about data quality and provenance?	
Should I do data imputation for missing data?	
Should I use sample randomization?	
What biases are in the data? Should I use a bias detection technique, like Fair Representation Learning or Casual Inference?	
What feature engineering should I do?	
Should I perform Exploratory Data Analysis (EDA) and discuss the generated data visualization with clinical experts?	
Should I remove outliers?	
What ML techniques should I use?	
Should I balance the classes? Is under-sampling or over-sampling preferable, or maybe a combination of the two?	
Should I balance the training set?	
Should I balance the test set?	
Is Model Ensemble Learning an avenue worth exploring?	
What evaluation techniques should I use?	
What evaluation metrics should I use?	
Should my approach avoid a certain type of error? E.g. Mean Average Error (MAE).	
Should I compare the performance with other approaches/algorithms?	
Should I care for real world prevalence?	
What confidence intervals should I use? E.g. in the anomaly detection problem.	
How should I compare to the other studies and results?	
What statistical tests should I employ?	

Table 6: Resilience aspects questionnaire.

Use-case/CODECO Component [insert the name of the solution/component/product you are developing]	
Leading entity	Identify the organisation that is leading the project
Leading responsible person	Identify the main responsible person leading the project. (Name and position in the organisation)
Team members involved	Identify the team members that are involved in the project. (For each member: name)
Checklist	Comments or observations
Security	
Have you tested the AI system for robustness against adversarial attacks?	What types of adversarial attacks have you considered? How do you mitigate potential vulnerabilities?
Which AI model encryption techniques are currently in use?	Are you using a specific encryption technique for the AI models that you may use. (i.e. Differential Privacy, White Noise, Homomorphic Encryption, Other)
How frequently are the encryption techniques reviewed and updated?	Have you specified the time range that you use as threshold to review your encryption techniques? If so, please specify (i.e. Annually, Monthly, as needed etc)
Have there been any incidents of security breaches related to AI model encryption in the past year?	Have you detected potential security breaches or attempts (y/n) - provide details?
Are there any measures to ensure compliance with data protection regulations when using AI model encryption techniques?	y/n), if so, please provide the measures (i.e., regular audits, automated compliance checks, etc)
Are there any data encryption techniques implemented in your system?	(y/n) if so please specify (i.e., Data Masking, Tokenization, White noise, other)

In which specific data-oriented operations are you utilizing encryption techniques?	Specify the operations (i.e, Data collection, data storage, data processing, data transmission)
What additional measures are taken to enhance data security during transit?	Please provide the measures if exists, (i.e, End-to-end encryption, multi-factor authentication, Regular network security assessments, other)
What are the key performance indicators (KPIs) used to measure the effectiveness of your security and resilience strategies?	Please provide different KPIs that you may use (i.e, Incident response time, Compliance audit results, other)
Are there measures to ensure the reliability of the system under various conditions?	
How do you simulate different operational conditions for testing?	
What redundancy measures are in place to ensure system reliability?	
Do you have contingency plans for system failures or unexpected behaviours?	
Are there predefined fallback mechanisms and if so, how often are these contingency plans reviewed and tested?	
Do you have an update plan and patch the AI system to address security vulnerabilities?	
What is the process for identifying and addressing vulnerabilities?	
How is the effectiveness of patches and updates evaluated	
Monitoring and Evaluation	
Does your evaluation methodology consider indicators to assess the performance of the considered ML/AI mechanisms such as resource footprint and actual response times, to further elaborate on the suitability of the chosen approaches?	Provide the indicators that you are using, e.g., memory, CPU, or energy consumption.
Do you plan to stress-test your AI solutions, focusing on aspects such as scalability, resource constraints and networking conditions? For example, to compare your ML/AI solution over high performance and limited resources servers.	Specify the methodological steps and the corresponding tools you are using
Do you plan to evaluate the performance over different Edge-Cloud architectures, e.g., over multi-cluster architectures?	Provide the characteristics of the employed architectures
Will you access the performance over real Edge-Cloud environments?	Provide the corresponding infrastructure you plan to utilize, e.g., testbed, server, or devices

Do you plan to investigate the impact of the different technological choices in the performance of your algorithms?	If yes, please describe, e.g., the networking solution or k8s distribution
Are you considering AD techniques to detect abnormal events, e.g., in performance metrics or the evaluated datasets or the observed data traces?	If yes, describe your approaches
Will you assess the end-to-end performance of your proposed ML/AI solutions?	Please describe how.
Do you plan to exploit the CODECO experimentation framework to assess the performance of your solutions?	If yes, please specify in what extend
Do you plan to provide part of your proposed ML/AI solutions in containerized versions to extend CODECO's experimental framework functionalities?	If yes, may you specify the software/platform the solution in written, e.g., MATLAB or Python.

Table 7: Continuous improvement and responsible AI use.

Use-case/CODECO Component [insert the name of the solution/component/product you are developing]	
Leading entity	Identify the organisation that is leading the project
Leading responsible person	Identify the main responsible person leading the project. (Name and position in the organisation)
Team members involved	Identify the team members that are involved in the project. (For each member: name)
Checklist	Comments or observations
Fairness and Bias Mitigation	
Have you assessed and mitigated biases in your training data?	
How frequently do you reassess the data for new biases?	
Are your algorithms tested for fairness across different demographic groups?	
What demographic groups have you considered in your fairness tests?	
How do you ensure diverse representation in your test groups?	
Have you conducted post-deployment bias assessments?	
How do you monitor for bias in real-time use cases?	
Have you taken specific steps to mitigate identified biases?	Provide examples of the mitigation techniques and explain how effective they were
Transparency and Explainability	
Can your AI model's decisions be easily explained to non-experts?	
Do you provide documentation or visual	Explain how you ensure explanations are

explanations of the model?	accessible to diverse audiences.
Have you documented the model's decision-making process?	Explain where it is – should be available in the Zenodo CODECO community
Is the documentation regularly updated and reviewed?	
Do CODECO stakeholders have access to the documentation?	
Are you using interpretable models or techniques like SHAP or LIME?	
How do you validate the accuracy of the explanations provided?	
Are you handling scenarios where the model's decision cannot be easily explained? Do you have a process for escalating such cases?	
Are there fallback mechanisms to provide alternative explanations?	
Accountability	
Is there a clear assignment of responsibility for AI decisions	
Who are the key CODECO stakeholders responsible for AI oversight?	
Have you established mechanisms for accountability and redress?	
What are the procedures for addressing user complaints and issues?	
How are responsibilities documented and communicated?	
Is there a clear process for investigating and resolving issues?	

Are there audit trails for AI decisions?	
How are decisions logged and monitored?	
Can the audit trails be easily accessed for review? How is accountability enforced and managed?	
Privacy and Data Protection	
Are you applying privacy protection policies in the data handling and user data storage process?	
What policies are in place for data access and storage?	
Are data access logs maintained and reviewed?	
Are you securing data both in transit and at rest	
Are encryption protocols used for data transmission?	
How is data encrypted at rest?	
Have you obtained explicit user consent for data collection and usage?	Explain How is consent documented and stored.
Are users informed of their rights and how to exercise them	
Do you have a plan to manage and respond to data breaches or privacy concerns?	What is the incident response plan for data breaches? How are users notified in the event of a data breach?
Safety and Reliability	
Do you have implemented safety protocols to ensure the AI operates correctly?	Are there safety guidelines and best practices in place? How are these protocols enforced and monitored?
Have you designed testing environments to validate the AI's performance under different	Describe the basic aspects

conditions?	
How is performance data collected and analysed?	
Are you monitoring and logging the AI's performance to detect and address issues proactively?	Describe the tools used
Human-centric Design	
Have you involved end-users in the design and development process?	Describe the methods used to gather insight and register feedback, e.g., surveys, interviews, etc.
How are user needs and preferences prioritized?	
How is feedback integrated into the development process?	
Do you ensure that the AI system is accessible to users with disabilities?	Describe accessibility standards and methods. Describe how compliance with the selected methods is verified.
Did you adjust based on user feedback and testing	If yes, please provide examples
How is the impact of these changes measured?	
Continuous Improvement Aspects	
Do you continuously monitor the AI system's performance and effectiveness?	Describe frequency, performance metrics, and tools used.
Have you integrated tools or processes for anomaly detection in the AI system?	Describe the tools and how anomalies are identified and reported; describe mitigation actions for anomaly detection
Do you review and update the AI model and its data? What is the schedule for regular reviews and updates?	Describe the schedule, how updates are documented, changes tracked, and communicated.
What is the process for integrating new research or technological advances?	
User Feedback and Interaction	
Are there dedicated channels for feedback?	Explain the kind of feedback channels are available for users to provide feedback on the AI system?
How is feedback collected and tracked?	
Do you have a priority strategy to address user feedback?	Which criteria are used to prioritize feedback?

How is feedback incorporated into the development roadmap?	
Do you provide a process for validating the effectiveness of changes made based on user feedback?	Provide examples; Are there follow-up surveys or tests conducted post-implementation?
How is user satisfaction measured after changes are made?	
How were these improvements identified and implemented? What has been the impact of these changes on the user experience?	

Annex II – Assessment Template

Table 8: Assessment template for AI governance and resilience in CODECO.

DIMENSIONS	CRITERIUM – Score (1-5)								
	Quality	Transparency	Usability	Compliance	Relevance	Security	Adaptability	Value Proposition	Comments
Governance									
Ethical principles									
How well does CODECO adhere to ethical guidelines?									
Are the ethical guidelines clearly communicated to all stakeholders?									
AI governance and lifecycle									
How effective is the AI governance structure throughout the lifecycle of CODECO's AI?									
Are governance procedures user-friendly and easy to implement?									
Stakeholders Engagement									
How actively are stakeholders involved in governance processes?									
Are stakeholder inputs and concerns effectively integrated into governance?									
Transparency, Explainability, Bias									
How transparent are the AI decision-making processes to stakeholders?									
How well can the AI system's decisions be explained to non-expert stakeholders?									

How effective is the system in identifying and mitigating biases?									
Resilience									
Security and robustness									
How robust are the security measures implemented in CODECO's AI system?									
Can the AI system adapt to new and emerging security threats?									
Error handling and control									
How effectively does the AI system handle errors and unexpected situations?									
Are error handling mechanisms user-friendly and easy to understand?									
Monitoring and evaluation									
How comprehensive and accurate is the monitoring system for AI performance?									
Is the monitoring system easy to use and interpret by the technical team?									
Continuous Improvement									
Responsible and sustainable use of AI in CODECO									
How well does CODECO ensure responsible and sustainable use of AI?									
Are sustainability practices relevant and effectively implemented within CODECO?									

Adaptation Measures									
How well does CODECO's AI system adapt to changes in architecture and operations?									
Do the adaptation measures provide significant value and improvement to the system?									

